

CyberFaces: a scalable and flexible online platform for web-based learning and workforce development for advanced cyberinfrastructure

Instructors and students

- Modular framework: Foundation, Expert, and Developer
- Curriculum delivery options
 - Modules
 - Courses
 - Badges and certificates
- Interactive learning materials (Jupyter Notebook)

System Design

- Open-source software stacks (Halcyon, JH, CILogon)
- Integration with GitHub, ACCESS
- Deployment on composable system
- Scalability support

Usage

- 85 modules and 11 courses
- Two in person workshops

The image displays two screenshots of the CyberFaces platform. The top screenshot shows the homepage with a dark blue background and a central illustration of a globe with books and a person. The main heading reads "Cyber-training for FAIR science in Climate and Environmental Sustainability". Below this, there is a search bar and three main sections: "Your Interests", "Level Up", and "Structured Lessons". The bottom screenshot shows a "Browse" page with a search bar and several filters on the left: Type (All, Modules, Courses), Rating (All, 4.5 & up, 4.0 & up, 3.5 & up, 3.0 & up), Level (Foundation, Expert, Developer), and Topics (ARIMA, climate, Climate Change Impacts on Agriculture, climate data). The main content area displays a grid of course cards, including "WaterSciCon24 Hands-On Workshop: Web-based Modules on Geospatial Data Processing Using Python", "Workshop: Web-based Modules on Geospatial Data Processing using Python", "Global Change and the Challenges of Sustainability Feeding a Growing Planet", "Python for Environmental Research", "iWater: A Cyber-enabled Data-driven Tool for Enhancing Hydrology Education", and "Short Course in Geospatial Data Extraction and Visualization". On the right side, there is a list of related resources and surveys, such as "WaterSciCon24 Pre-workshop Survey" and "Geospatial & Hydrological Science: DEM Accessing using a Shapefile".